

Enhancing Project Performance through Risk Reduction: Evidence from Tea System Automation in Kenya

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between project risk mitigation and the performance of the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya. As automation efforts intensify within firms managed by the Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA), addressing risks associated with technological adoption has become critical to ensuring project success. The research explored how minimizing key risks — including technological setbacks and operational interruptions — impacts the efficiency, reliability, and overall effectiveness of the automation process. A descriptive research design was employed, focusing on project managers, executives, and other primary stakeholders involved in the implementation. Specifically, the study targeted 69 project managers, 69 project coordinators, and 207 project committee executives, amounting to 345 participants. The sampling frame comprised 69 active KTDA-managed tea processing firms, from which a sample of 185 individuals was randomly selected using the Taro Yamane (1967) sampling formula. The findings indicate that while risk mitigation strengthens project stability and concentration, it demands thorough planning and active stakeholder engagement to prevent disruptions and accountability challenges. The study's outcomes underscore the importance of effective risk management practices in enhancing the performance of tea system automation initiatives within KTDA-managed entities and similar environments.

Keywords: *Project Risk Reduction, Tea System Automation, Project Performance, Risk Management, Technological Implementation.*

JEL Classification codes: *H43, O22, D81 & G32.*

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Introduction

Background Information

Project risk mitigation is a fundamental component of risk management strategies in industries as diverse as agriculture, construction and information technology. It involves minimizing the potential negative impacts of specific risks through proactive measures, such as risk assessments,

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preventative actions, and control mechanisms (Kerzner, 2017). By focusing on reducing the likelihood or impact of these risks, project managers can enhance project performance and stability while maintaining greater control over critical project elements. According to Busiliru et al. (2024), “risk reduction is particularly effective for managing risks within the project team’s control, such as technical issues, operational delays, or safety hazards”.

The implementation of complex projects such as agricultural automation is inherently fraught with risks that can threaten timelines, budgets and quality standards. For the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya, these risks include potential technology failures, supply chain delays, and regulatory compliance challenges (Busiliru et al., 2024). Reducing these risks through targeted strategies—such as improving system reliability, enhancing supplier contracts, and staying abreast of regulatory requirements—helps prevent project derailments (Hillson & Simon, 2020). By proactively addressing potential issues, project managers can manage uncertainties more effectively and ensure project objectives are met.

However, risk reduction is not without its challenges. Successful implementation requires thorough risk assessments, effective communication, and stakeholder engagement to ensure that risk mitigation strategies are properly understood and executed (Aven, 2016). Insufficient planning and coordination can lead to oversights and cost increases, potentially negating the benefits of risk reduction efforts. Moreover, while risk reduction lowers the probability or impact of certain risks, it cannot eliminate them entirely. Continuous monitoring and adjustment of risk strategies are crucial to handle emerging issues and maintain effective mitigation measures throughout the project lifecycle (Ward & Chapman, 2011). Thus, while risk reduction is a valuable approach in project management, it must be integrated into a comprehensive risk management framework to optimize project success.

Ideally, the implementation of automation initiatives in agriculture, such as Kenya’s Tea System Automation Project, would unfold without major obstacles, with all potential risks being effectively anticipated and mitigated. Advanced technologies would be incorporated smoothly, boosting productivity, lowering operational costs, and delivering high-quality outcomes (Sparrow & Bromage, 2020). Project managers would adopt proactive risk reduction measures, enabling them to focus on key project activities and maintain overall stability (Hillson & Simon, 2020). Through coordinated planning and execution, such projects would be completed within set timelines and budgets, fostering the growth and long-term sustainability of the agricultural sector (Kerzner, 2017; PMI, 2021).

However, in reality, automation projects within agriculture often encounter significant challenges. The Tea System Automation Project in Kenya, for instance, has experienced various risks, including technological breakdowns, disruptions in supply chains, and difficulties in regulatory compliance (Mwangi, 2019). Despite efforts to manage these risks, shortcomings such as poor planning, weak stakeholder coordination, and ambiguous contractual agreements have led to increased costs, project delays, and a decline in quality standards (Aven, 2016). Mwangi (2019) observed that approximately 60% of agricultural projects in Kenya suffered delays attributable to ineffective risk management strategies. These issues highlight the intricate nature of managing risks in large-scale automation efforts and reveal the limitations inherent in current risk mitigation practices.

While existing research has explored risk management across various sectors, there remains a notable gap in understanding how specific risk reduction efforts influence the performance of agricultural automation projects. Much of the literature has concentrated on broader risk management approaches or on industries such as construction and information technology, with relatively little attention given to the distinct challenges of agricultural automation (Aven, 2016). A 2021 survey by the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS) reported that only 15% of

agricultural projects had implemented comprehensive risk reduction frameworks. This study seeks to address this gap by investigating the relationship between risk reduction and the performance of the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya. In doing so, it aims to contribute practical insights for enhancing risk management strategies and improving project outcomes within the agricultural automation sector, thereby enriching the broader discipline of project management.

Research Objective

The objective of this research is to investigate the impact of project risk reduction on the performance of the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya, with the broader goal of enhancing risk management strategies to improve project outcomes within the Kenyan tea industry.

Research Hypothesis

The null hypothesis (H_0) is that reducing project risk has no significant effect on the performance of the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya.

Theoretical Review

Contingency Theory, initially developed by scholars like Joan Woodward, posits that organizational practices should adapt to specific internal and external factors, such as technology, organizational size, task uncertainty, and environmental conditions. In project management, this theory suggests that there is no single approach that suits all projects; instead, strategies and structures must align with each project's unique demands (Schwelbe, 2018). Applied to risk reduction in the Kenya Tea Development Agency's system automation projects, Contingency Theory supports the idea that project managers should tailor risk management strategies to accommodate the complexity, size, and uncertainty of each project. Flexible decision-making processes are essential, enabling managers to adjust as project conditions evolve (Wada et al., 2018).

Critics of Contingency Theory, however, argue that this flexibility may complicate decision-making and resource allocation, potentially leading to delays or missed risks in large-scale projects like KTDA's automation initiative (Tseng & Tan, 2018; Liao et al., 2018). Additionally, identifying appropriate performance metrics in such complex projects can be challenging, as Contingency Theory provides limited guidance on selecting and interpreting metrics in uncertain environments (Clark, 2019).

Despite these challenges, Contingency Theory offers a framework for KTDA project managers to create customized risk reduction strategies and performance metrics that reflect project-specific needs. Metrics should include adherence to timelines, budgetary control, quality standards, stakeholder satisfaction, and sustainability goals, regularly reviewed and adjusted to align with evolving project dynamics (Pinto & Slevin, 2018). By applying these principles, project managers can better manage risk reduction and enhance the performance of automation projects within KTDA-managed firms.

Conceptual Model and Hypothesis

The conceptual framework of this study sought to demonstrate the relationship between project risk reduction and the performance of a tea system automation project in Kenya. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Busiliru at al., 2024

Empirical Literature

Singh, Deep, and Banerjee (2017) investigated impact of risk management approaches performance of construction companies in India. Questionnaires were designed to collect data. Target was 152 project team members from three construction firms. According to the findings, all three construction companies used risk-prevention techniques to assess how well building projects turned out, including safety inspections, safety systems, contingency planning, and detailed work plans. Other risk prevention methods that contribute in reaching project objectives on time, according to the study findings. Jaber (2020) evaluated impact of risk management approaches on performance of insurance businesses in Jordan. Data was collected from 120 insurance business managers via questionnaires. According to the statistics, the majority of businesses have been in existence for a long period. Risk management approaches' effectiveness had a major impact on organizational performance.

Bhoola, Hiremath, and Mallik (2014) evaluated risk management approaches utilized in Indian software development projects. The research sample included 302 project managers. According to study's findings, in software development initiatives, the risk reduction approach had the best results. The only way that other risk management techniques, such avoidance, transference, and acceptance, were implemented was through open dialogue with stakeholders. Hailu (2018) aimed to identify the primary risk factors that face building construction projects in Addis Abeba, as well as the effectiveness of risk preventive and mitigation techniques. The sample included 35 building contractors. The outcomes of the study revealed that building contractors lacked new risk-mitigation tactics, did not apply risk-analysis approaches, and depended mainly on direct judgment in estimating timelines and costs. The results show that better contract forms that handle issues including clarity, duties and responsibilities, risk allocation, dispute resolution, and payment are urgently needed.

Aimable, Shukla, and Oduor (2015) studied effects of risk management techniques on construction project performance in Rwanda. A descriptive research design was used for the investigation. The target population was 291 project team members, of which 169 were sampled. Questionnaires, documentary reviews, and in-depth interview schedules were used to collect data. The results showed that the performance of construction projects is affected by a thorough work plan, safety inspections, and the presence of a safety system. The study found that the performance of construction firms was influenced by the research prevention method.

Aimable, Shukla, and Oduor (2015) studied influence of risk management systems on the performance of construction projects in Rwanda. The target population consisted of 291 project team members, 169 of whom were sampled. Data was gathered using questionnaires, documentary reviews, and interviews. The results demonstrated that a thorough work plan, safety inspections,

and the presence of a safety system all affect how well construction projects turn out. The study came to the conclusion that the performance of construction enterprises was affected by the research preventative method.

This study employed a descriptive research design to examine the relationship between project risk transference strategies and the performance of the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya. According to the Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA), it manages 69 active tea processing firms, which served as the units of analysis for this research. The units of observation (target population) comprised 345 individuals, including 69 project managers, 69 project coordinators, and 207 committee executives.

To determine the appropriate sample size, Slovin's formula was applied, as the target population consisted of a large number of units (employees and board members) (Zimmermann, 2023). The study assumed a 95% confidence level, corresponding to a standardized normal deviate value of 1.96, and an acceptable margin of error of 5% (or 0.05). The sample size for this study was therefore calculated using Slovin's formula for large populations, as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2} \quad (1)$$

Where: n = Sample size,

N = Total population and

e = Error tolerance (confidence level).

Since the population $N = 345$,

Error tolerance = 0.05,

The sample size was determined as:

$$n = \frac{345}{1 + 345 \cdot (0.05)^2} = 185$$

Therefore, the sample size will be 185

Results

A regression analysis was conducted to determine the proportion of the performance of a tea system automation project in Kenya (dependent variable) that could be predicted by the project risk mitigation strategy (independent variable). Table 1 presents the model summary for the relationship between Risk Reduction and Project Performance. The correlation coefficient (R) of 0.401 indicates a moderate positive relationship between Risk Reduction and project performance. The R-Square value of 0.161 suggests that 16.1% of the variance in Project Performance is explained by Risk Reduction. After adjusting for the number of predictors, the Adjusted R-Square is 0.143, meaning that 14.3% of the variance in performance is attributable to Risk Reduction when controlling for other variables. The standard error of the estimate (0.76594) indicates moderate prediction error, suggesting that while Risk Reduction has a notable impact, other factors also play a role in determining project performance. These results imply that although Risk Reduction

strategies contribute positively to Project Performance, their influence is somewhat limited, and additional risk management practices are required for optimal outcomes. This aligns with previous studies, such as Kerzner (2017) and PMI (2021), which suggest that while reducing risks can improve project outcomes by mitigating potential setbacks, it should be complemented by other strategies like risk avoidance or transference to achieve stronger results. The implication is that while Risk Reduction is essential, organizations must adopt a more comprehensive risk management approach to enhance overall project performance.

Table 1. Model Summary (Risk Reduction against Project Performance)

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.401	.161	.143	.76594

The ANOVA results in Table 2 demonstrate that Risk Reduction has a statistically significant effect on Project Performance. The regression sum of squares (220.231) and the F-statistic of 29.744, with a p-value of 0.000, indicate that the model is highly significant. This means that the variation in Project Performance explained by Risk Reduction is not due to chance. However, the residual sum of squares (1147.666) and a relatively high mean square error (7.404) suggest that a considerable portion of project performance is influenced by factors other than Risk Reduction. The findings imply that while Risk Reduction contributes positively to Project Performance, its impact is somewhat limited, accounting for only part of the total variance. This is consistent with the literature, such as studies by Chapman and Ward (2011) and PMI (2021), which emphasize that Risk Reduction, while crucial, must be integrated with other risk management practices to optimize project outcomes. The implication is that organizations should not solely rely on Risk Reduction but also implement complementary strategies, like Risk Avoidance or Risk Transference, to improve overall project performance and minimize the residual risks affecting outcomes.

Table 2. ANOVA Statistics (Risk Reduction against Project Performance)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	220.231	1	220.231	29.744	.000
Residual	1147.666	155	7.404		
Total	1367.897	156			

Table 3 presents the coefficients of the independent variable (risk reduction) and the dependent variable (performance of the tea development automation system project). These findings show that the project performance will be having an index of 11.456 when risk reduction is held constant. Furthermore, the relationship between risk reduction and project performance had a beta coefficient of 0.439. This shows that project performance would improve by 0.501 for every unit improvement in risk reduction. The t – value (2.659) of more than +1.96 indicates that the change in project performance by risk reduction is not by chance. The P value (0.000) was less than the significance level (0.05), so the relationship is significant. Thus, yielding a regression model where $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$. The general form of the equation was to predict project performance $X_1 =$ Risk Reduction; $Y = 11.456 + 0.439X_1$. This indicates that project performance = 11.456 + 0.439* Risk Reduction. Therefore, we can conclude that risk reduction positively and significantly influences performance of tea development automation system project in Kenya (Vikiru, et al., 2023).

The study results of the survey in Table 3 revealed that there was positive and significant relationship between risk reduction and performance of tea development automation system

project ($\beta_1=0.439$, $t_{cal}= 2.659 > t_{critical} =1.96$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$). The null hypothesis (H_{01}): Risk Reduction has no significant relationship with performance of tea development automation system project in Kenya or ($H_{01}: \beta_1 \neq 0$) is therefore rejected and concluded that risk reduction (X_i) positively and significantly influences performance of tea development automation system project in Kenya (Y).

Table 3. Regression Coefficients (Risk Reduction against Project Performance)

Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	11.456	.878		13.047	.000
Risk Reduction	.439	.165	.401	2.659	.000

Discussion

The regression analysis shows a positive and statistically significant relationship between risk mitigation strategies and the performance of the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya. With a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.401, the findings indicate a moderate positive association, suggesting that effective risk reduction can contribute to better project outcomes. Specifically, the R-Square value of 0.161 shows that 16.1% of the variation in project performance can be attributed to risk reduction efforts, while the adjusted R-Square of 0.143 indicates that this effect remains significant even when controlling for other variables. The standardized Beta coefficient of 0.439 further supports that for every unit increase in risk reduction, project performance improves by 0.439 units. Additionally, the statistically significant t-value (2.659) and p-value (< 0.05) validate that this relationship is not due to chance. These results underscore the importance of risk reduction as a critical strategy for enhancing the performance of complex automation projects like those managed by KTDA.

However, the study also reveals that while risk reduction significantly contributes to project performance, its impact is somewhat limited, as evidenced by the considerable residual variance in project performance (83.9%). This suggests that other factors, perhaps including risk avoidance, risk transference, or even external environmental factors, also play a substantial role in influencing project success. These findings align with the broader literature, such as works by Chapman and Ward (2011) and PMI (2021), which emphasize that risk management is most effective when it incorporates multiple strategies. Consequently, the implication for project managers and policymakers in KTDA and similar contexts is that while risk reduction is essential, a more comprehensive approach that includes other complementary risk management practices is necessary to fully optimize project outcomes and minimize residual risks. This layered approach to risk management can provide a more robust framework for achieving the desired performance and sustainability in large-scale agricultural automation projects.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that risk mitigation has a positive and significant impact on the performance of the Tea System Automation Project in Kenya, although the impact is moderate. This suggests that while effective risk reduction enhances project outcomes, it should be integrated with additional risk management practices to address the full range of project uncertainties. Adopting a comprehensive risk management approach can further improve project performance and contribute to the long-term success and sustainability of automation initiatives within KTDA. It is

recommended that the Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA) adopt a comprehensive risk management framework that integrates risk reduction with complementary strategies such as risk transference, avoidance, and monitoring. This multi-faceted approach would enable KTDA to address the various uncertainties that impact project performance, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of automation initiatives. Additionally, regular training for project managers on adaptive risk management practices and the importance of proactive stakeholder engagement would further support project success and sustainability.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interests

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